
Research

An Overview of China's OFDI, Export Trade, and Formal Institutions in Africa and Asia

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Abstract: In this article, I will describe the analysis of China's Outward Foreign Direct Investment and export trade with Africa and Asia. I will start with the industrial structure of China's OFDI in both regions, outlining the industry's core to its investment. In the following section, those particular countries that come out to be the biggest receivers of Chinese investments will be discussed, and an attempt will be made to elaborate on the strategic and economic reasons behind such choices. This will lead to an analysis of the current trade volume and composition of exports between China and its African and Asian partners, enabling us to gain insight into the nature and dynamics of these trade relationships. We will look, finally, into the institutional factors in Africa and Asia influencing Chinese OFDI and trade. In this paper, a comprehensive overview will be given, taking into consideration the complexity and strategic relevance of China's economic engagements with Africa and Asia.

Keywords: OFDI, Export Trade, Formal Institutions, Africa and Asia

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1. The Current Situation of Chinese OFDI to Africa and Asia

Chinese outward foreign direct investment (OFDI) has become increasingly significant in global FDI, driven by the "Going Out" policy implemented in 2000 to leverage its surplus capacity and enhance international cooperation (Wang and Zhao 2017; Yu and Liu 2019). This initiative resulted in a clear policy direction, engaging investors with domestic imperatives and encouraging local firms to expand internationally. Since then, Chinese OFDI has grown substantially, with Africa and Asia continuing to receive a significant portion of its global distribution. Chinese firms have likely found it more feasible to invest in Africa and Asia than to compete with established enterprises in the developed world. Additionally, investing in these regions is congruent with China's strategic objectives and its increasing demand for raw materials. Driven by domestic policies and international capital demands, China has become the second-largest source of foreign investment globally, behind the United States. In 2022, China's outbound foreign direct investment reached 147.85 billion USD. That same year, Chinese investment in Asia amounted to 117.12 billion USD, representing

79.2% of its total OFDI, with member countries of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) receiving 14.06 billion USD, or 12% of that total (MOFCOM 2023¹; UNCTAD 2023²)

1.1 The industries of Chinese OFDI in Africa and Asia

China's Outward Foreign Direct Investment (OFDI) has become a significant element of its global economic strategy, particularly in Africa and Asia. These investments reflect China's broader goals of enhancing connectivity, securing vital resources, and supporting sustainable development through diverse sectoral engagements. The following sections explore the distribution of Chinese OFDI across various industries in these two regions, highlighting the strategic focus and impact of these investments.

(a) The industries of Chinese OFDI in Africa

Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of Chinese outward foreign direct investment (OFDI) in various sectors across African countries for 2023. The largest shares of Chinese OFDI are in the Transport and Energy sectors, each accounting for 33% of the total investment. This significant investment in infrastructure and energy reflects China's strategic interest in improving connectivity and securing energy resources, supporting initiatives such as the Belt and Road Initiative (Chinese Investment Tracker, AEI, 2023³). Investments in the Transport sector emphasise China's commitment to developing key infrastructure projects, such as railways, ports, and highways, which facilitate trade and enhance connectivity within Africa. High-profile projects like the Mombasa-Nairobi Standard Gauge Railway in Kenya exemplify China's dedication to improving transportation infrastructure (MOFCOM, 2023). The substantial investment in the Energy sector indicates China's focus on securing long-term access to vital energy resources, including oil, gas, and renewable energy sources. Chinese companies are involved in significant energy projects across Africa, contributing to the continent's energy diversification and sustainability efforts (China-Briefing, 2023⁴).

Figure 1 Sectors of China OFDI in African countries

Source: Chinese investment tracker, AEI

Metals and Real Estate sectors each account for 11% of the investment, highlighting China's interest in industrial and urban development. Investments in the Metals sector support mining activities essential for China's manufacturing

¹ <http://english.mofcom.gov.cn/article/newsrelease/press/202311/20231103452116.shtml>

² <https://unctad.org/publication/world-investment-report-2023>

³ <https://www.aei-conference.org/>

⁴ <https://www.china-briefing.com/>

industries, while Real Estate investments involve urban development projects that bolster urbanisation trends in African countries (MOFCOM, 2023). Utilities receive 4% of the investment, demonstrating China's role in improving essential services like water supply, electricity, and waste management. These are crucial for enhancing the quality of life and supporting sustainable development. The Technology sector, accounting for 3% of the investment, reflects China's efforts to advance technological infrastructure in Africa, including telecommunications and information technology, which are vital for economic growth and innovation. The finance and Agriculture sectors each receive 2% of the investment, indicating China's support for financial services, banking infrastructure, and agricultural productivity, which is essential for economic stability and food security in African countries. Other sectors comprise the remaining 1% of the investment, showcasing a diversified strategy aimed at comprehensive economic engagement with Africa. This approach ensures that Chinese investments contribute to various aspects of economic development, supporting balanced and inclusive growth across the continent.

(b) The industries of Chinese OFDI in Asia

In recent years, China's Outward Foreign Direct Investment (OFDI) has emerged as a pivotal component of its economic strategy, particularly within the Asian region. The rapid economic growth and industrial upgrading in Asia have provided a fertile ground for Chinese investments, facilitating the diversification of investment portfolios and the enhancement of economic ties with neighbouring countries. This paper examines the scope and distribution of China's OFDI across various sectors in Asia, as highlighted by Table 1, which illustrates the extensive reach of Chinese investments within the national economies of the region.

China's OFDI strategy is characterised by a broad and dynamic investment approach that aligns with the region's economic advancements. The leasing and business services, financial services, and manufacturing sectors constitute the largest shares of Chinese OFDI. In 2022, financial services alone absorbed US\$28.5 billion, accounting for 19.3% of total OFDI flows, demonstrating a significant year-on-year increase. This substantial investment reflects China's strategic focus on expanding its financial influence and integrating more deeply into the global financial system.

The manufacturing sector also saw robust investments, totalling US\$25.6 billion, with a strategic emphasis on high-tech manufacturing industries such as automotive and electronics. This focus is indicative of China's ambition to ascend the global value chain in manufacturing. Investments in wholesale and retail trade amounted to US\$20.3 billion, underscoring China's commitment to developing distribution networks and retail infrastructure essential for trade facilitation and consumer market growth.

Table 1 Sectoral distribution of China's OFDI flows, 2022 (Billions of US dollars)

Industry	Flows (Billions of US dollars)	Year-on-year growth rate (%)	Share (%)
Leasing and business services	36.3	-1.6	24.9
Financial services	28.5	52.3	19.3
Manufacturing	25.6	108.5	17.5
Wholesale and retail trade	20.3	5.1	13.7
Mining	11.3	-32.0	7.7
Real estate	7.8	17.9	5.3
Information transmission, software and IT services	8.9	115.2	6.0
Construction	3.7	10.0	2.6

Scientific research and technical services	4.6	100.5	3.1
Transportation, storage and postal services	2.7	-34.7	1.9
Agricultural, forestry, animal husbandry and fishery	2.6	26.4	1.8
Production and supply of electricity, heat, gas, water	2.1	21.0	1.5
Culture, sports and entertainment	3.1	236.6	2.1
Resident services, repairs and other services	1.6	-3.2	1.1
Water conservancy, environment and public facility	1.9	148.1	1.2
Hotels and catering	1.2	195.5	0.8
Others	0.1	-	0.1

Source: Ministry of Commerce of the People's Republic of China (MOFCOM), 2023; China-Briefing, 2023

Moreover, Chinese investments in information transmission, software, and IT services reached US\$8.9 billion, highlighting the sector's robust growth trajectory and the increasing importance of the digital economy. Investments in scientific research and technical services, amounting to US\$4.6 billion, emphasise China's dedication to innovation and technological development, which are critical for sustaining long-term economic growth and maintaining a competitive edge in various industries.

In addition to these sectors, China's OFDI in the culture, sports, and entertainment sectors saw a notable increase, with investments rising to US\$3.1 billion. This growth is a testament to China's efforts to expand its cultural influence and promote its soft power globally. The water conservancy and public facility management sectors received US\$1.9 billion, showcasing a 148.1% growth and reflecting China's focus on sustainable development and environmental protection. The hotels and catering sectors, which received US\$1.2 billion, support the development of tourism infrastructure, which is vital for promoting tourism and enhancing cultural exchanges. These diverse investments illustrate China's comprehensive and strategic approach to OFDI, aimed at strengthening economic ties, enhancing technological capabilities, and promoting sustainable development across Asia. China's OFDI in Africa and Asia demonstrates a comprehensive and strategic approach, focusing on key sectors that support infrastructure development, energy security, technological advancement, and sustainable growth. In Africa, the emphasis on transport and energy highlights China's commitment to enhancing connectivity and securing resources, while in Asia, investments span a wide range of industries, underscoring China's ambition to integrate into the global financial system and advance technologically. Overall, these investments reflect China's broader economic goals of fostering regional ties, promoting innovation, and supporting sustainable development.

1.2 The countries of Chinese OFDI in Africa and Asia

Chinese Outward Foreign Direct Investment (OFDI) has shown a strategic and geographically concentrated pattern, particularly in Africa and Asia. OFDI in Africa is highly concentrated, with 50% of projects directed to only four

destinations: South Africa (about 20%), Morocco, Egypt, and Nigeria (around 9%–10% each). The distribution of these investments reflects China's strategic interests in the continent. According to the UNCTAD World Investment Report, 73% of all assets in Africa originate from advanced economies, 25% from emerging countries, and the remaining from developing countries⁵. At the beginning of the period (2004–2008), Chinese investments primarily targeted South Africa, Nigeria, and Egypt. Over the years, China has consolidated its presence in North Africa, with Egypt, Algeria, and Morocco becoming significant recipients of Chinese capital⁶. Outward foreign direct investments (OFDIs) in North African countries serve as strategic platforms for accessing the European market due to their geographic proximity and significant investments in infrastructure development. Other regions have similarly developed strong economic ties with China. For example, in Ethiopia, China has emerged as the leading investor, particularly in Special Economic Zones (SEZs), where investments are concentrated in labor-intensive sectors such as shoe manufacturing, textiles, and leather goods processing. These sectors cater to both domestic and export markets. In Zambia, China is the third-largest investor, with a focus on intensive extractive activities that often surpass the investment levels of many advanced countries. In Asia, Chinese OFDI has been robust, with significant investments in both advanced and emerging economies. Southeast Asia, in particular, has seen a surge in Chinese investments. Countries like Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, and Vietnam have become key destinations due to their strategic locations, market potential, and favourable investment climates.

According to the Asian Development Bank (ADB)⁷, Chinese investments in Asia are driven by factors such as the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which aims to enhance regional connectivity and cooperation. In South Asia, Pakistan has been a major recipient of Chinese OFDI, largely due to the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). This flagship BRI project includes infrastructure development, energy projects, and Gwadar Port expansion.

In advanced Asian economies like Japan and South Korea, Chinese investments have focused on technology acquisition and strategic partnerships. The collaboration often includes joint ventures in high-tech industries, research and development, and financial services. Particularly in Southeast Asia, Chinese firms' investments are shifting towards more advanced manufacturing and processing of critical raw materials. The financial services sector accounted for a significant number of transactions, while the basic materials sector was the top industry by value.

Table 2 shows that China's OFDI stock in all different Asian regions shows an increasing trend from 2006 to 2017, except for a few years. At the end of 2017, China had the largest OFDI stock in ASEAN countries, which accounted for 59.55% of the total, followed by Western Asia, accounting for 12.90%, and by South Asia and Central Asia countries, accounting for 8.31% and 7.81%, respectively. This indicates that China is continuously increasing its OFDI in Asia countries, while the distribution of China's OFDI in these countries is unbalanced. In addition, the average annual growth rate (AAGR) of China's OFDI in ASEAN (43.7876%), South Asia (64.9569%) and Central Asia countries (40.4119%) is higher than the overall average (37.3024%). At the same time, the AAGR of China's OFDI in West Asia (31.0048) is lower than the overall average. These investments reflect China's broader strategy of diversifying its investments and engaging with emerging markets in both Africa and Asia.

Table 2 China's OFDI Stock in Different Asian Regions from 2006 to 2017 (Unit: 0.1 billion)

ASEAN Countries	West Asia Countries	South Asia Countries	Central Asia Countries	Central-Eastern European Countries	CIS Countries	Overall
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⁵ AFRICA CHINA ECONOMY. (2023). <https://africachinapresscentre.org/2023/11/03/china-africa-to-keep-deepening-industrial-chain-cooperation/>

⁶ <https://www.sais-cari.org/chinese-investment-in-africa>

⁷ Asian Development Bank (ADB). (2023). Asian Economic Integration Report

2006	6.5725	7.0662	6.5598	6.5555	7.2529	6.9603	6.9080
2007	6.5851	7.0803	6.5624	6.6458	7.2663	7.0187	6.9313
2008	6.5740	7.0686	6.5835	6.6815	7.2615	7.0518	6.9340
2009	6.6228	7.1333	6.5914	6.7332	7.3016	7.1098	6.9812
2010	6.6583	7.1167	6.6522	6.6571	7.2952	7.0709	6.9789
2011	6.6775	7.0484	6.6263	6.6173	7.2696	7.0664	6.9652
2012	6.6779	7.0942	6.6640	6.6801	7.2918	7.0485	6.9809
2013	6.7077	7.0970	6.7017	6.7201	7.2906	7.0961	6.9958
2014	6.7305	7.1177	6.7240	6.6890	7.2875	7.0859	7.0036
2015	6.7788	7.2069	6.7546	6.6949	7.2991	7.1142	7.0453
2016	6.8063	7.2340	6.7739	6.7057	7.3128	7.1150	7.0622
2017	6.8069	7.2390	6.8077	6.6839	7.3201	7.1149	7.0633
AAGR (%)	0.3194	0.1840	0.3384	0.1790	0.0852	0.2008	0.2013

Source: Data are derived from calculations and the Statistical Bulletin of China's Outward Foreign Direct Investment

2 The current situation of the China-Africa Asia trade

China's trade with Africa and Asia has been significant in recent years. China's total merchandise trade with Sub-Saharan Africa has increased by 1864% since 2001, with its trade with Africa reaching a record high of \$282 billion in 2023. China remains Africa's largest trading partner by far in terms of total volume. Still, its trade relationships with other major economies in Asia, such as India and South Korea, have also grown rapidly. The trade between China and Africa is characterised by China mostly importing raw materials from Africa while exporting more manufactured goods. This has led to a trade deficit in Africa, which has raised concerns about the sustainability of the trade relationship. Despite China's dominant position in Africa's trade, other Asian countries are also expanding their trade ties with the continent, offering alternative sources of financing and trade partnerships. The data from the China Africa Research Initiative shows that China's trade with Africa has been steadily increasing for the past two decades, with weak commodity prices since 2014 impacting the value of African exports to China. Overall, China's trade with Africa and Asia is a complex and evolving landscape, influenced by factors such as commodity prices, trade imbalances, and the growing trade relationships with other Asian countries.

2.1 The volume of China trade with its partner

As of 2021, exports from China to Africa amounted to roughly 145 billion U.S. dollars, up from 113 billion U.S. dollars in 2020. Overall, Chinese trade with African countries has increased over the last two decades. In 2000, Africa imported goods from China valued at five billion U.S. dollars. Moreover, a peak in the value of imports from China was registered in 2015 at 155 billion U.S. dollars (figure 2).

Figure 2 Value of Chinese exports to Africa from 2000 to 2021

Source: Self-organized by the author based on UN Comtrade

As of 2021, Nigeria and South Africa were the main importers from China in Africa, importing approximately 22.6 billion and 21.1 billion U.S. dollars, respectively. Chinese exports to Egypt followed closely, with a value of 18.3 billion U.S. dollars. Overall, trade between African countries and China has been increasing over the last two decades. In 2020, Chinese exports to Africa were valued at 113.96 billion U.S. dollars (figure 3).

Figure 3 Value of Chinese exports to Africa in 2021 by country

Source: Self-organized by the author based on UN Comtrade

The trajectory of China's exports to Asia over the past two decades reflects the country's profound integration into regional trade dynamics. From 2001 to 2022, China's exports to Asia witnessed remarkable growth, surging from \$141.31 billion to \$1.73 trillion. This expansion underscores China's pivotal role as a major exporter within the Asian continent. The early 2000s marked a period of steady ascent, with exports consistently increasing year over year, reflecting China's emergence as the world's factory and its growing importance in global supply chains. This growth was further fueled by factors such as the liberalisation of trade policies, improvements in infrastructure, and the competitiveness of Chinese goods in international markets. However, the global financial crisis of 2008 momentarily disrupted this trajectory, causing a slight dip in exports before they resumed their upward trend. Subsequently, China's exports to Asia experienced robust expansion throughout the following decade, driven by initiatives such as the Belt and Road Initiative, which aimed to enhance connectivity and trade linkages across Asia and beyond. Moreover, China's increasing focus on innovation and technology-intensive industries contributed to the diversification and sophistication of its export portfolio. Nevertheless, challenges such as trade tensions with the United States and geopolitical dynamics within the region have introduced uncertainties that could impact future export trends. Overall, the evolution of China's exports to Asia underscores the country's significance in driving regional economic integration and its enduring influence on global trade dynamics (figure 4).

Figure 4 China export trade to Asia

Source: Self-organized by the author based on the Trade map website

In 2021, China's export trade with the top 10 countries in Asia showcased the region's pivotal role in the global economy. Leading the pack were Japan and South Korea, with trade values of 165.82 billion and 148.85 billion dollars, respectively, underscoring the enduring economic partnerships and robust bilateral relations shared with China. The trade dynamics with Vietnam, India, and Malaysia further emphasised the diversified trade portfolio within the region, with export values reaching 137.90 billion, 97.51 billion, and 78.70 billion dollars, respectively. Thailand, Indonesia, and the Philippines also emerged as significant trading partners, with export values totalling 69.36 billion, 60.65 billion, and 57.31 billion dollars, respectively, highlighting the depth of economic interdependence and cooperation. Additionally, the United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia played crucial roles in China's export landscape, with trade values of 43.82 billion and 30.32 billion dollars, respectively, reflecting the region's strategic importance in driving global economic growth and fostering mutually beneficial trade relationships (figure 5).

Figure 5 China export trade to the 10 top countries in ASIA

Source: Self-organized by the author based on the World Bank Top of Form

2.2 Commodity composition of export

In 2021, China's exports to different regions showcased varying compositions and emphases. In South Asia, capital goods constituted 41.31% of exports, representing vital machinery and equipment contributing to infrastructure and industrial development in the region. Consumer goods followed, comprising 19.21% of exports, highlighting China's role in catering to consumer demand with a diverse range of products. Intermediate goods accounted for a significant share of 38.44%, underlining China's position as a key supplier of components and materials for manufacturing processes in South Asia. In the East Asia & Pacific region, capital goods dominated exports, comprising 49.68% of the total, reflecting the region's focus on industrialisation and infrastructure development. Consumer goods constituted 11.93%, emphasising China's contribution to meeting consumer needs in the area. Intermediate goods, at 19.61%, showcased China's integral role in the regional supply chain. In Sub-Saharan Africa, capital goods accounted for 28.99% of exports, reflecting investments in infrastructure and industrial projects. Consumer goods, at 42.23%, demonstrated China's engagement with the growing consumer market in the region. Intermediate goods represented 28.11%, highlighting China's support for local manufacturing activities. Raw materials constituted a smaller share, underscoring China's focus on higher value-added exports. Overall, these export patterns underscore China's diverse contributions to regional economies across South Asia, East Asia & Pacific, and Sub-Saharan Africa, catering to different developmental needs and consumer preferences (table 3).

Table 3 Export trade from China

	South Asia		East Asia & Pacific		Sub-Saharan Africa	
	Export (US\$ Thousand)	Export Product Share (%)	Export (US\$ Thousand)	Export Product Share (%)	Export (US\$ Thousand)	Export Product Share (%)
All Products						
Capital goods	63633059.61	41.31	582304543.5	49.68	31697915.31	28.99
Consumer goods	29583758.76	19.21	139882440.6	11.93	46176190.29	42.23
Intermediate goods	59213334.52	38.44	229883695.1	19.61	30738073.75	28.11

Raw materials	1512422.94	0.98	209547137.2	17.88	668589.45	0.61
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Source, Made by the author based on World Bank

3 Institutional Factors in Africa and Asia

The institutional factors are derived from the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) project, which is a research initiative by the World Bank. The WGI reports aggregate and individual governance indicators for over 200 countries and territories for six dimensions of governance.

Figure 6: Institutional Factors in Africa and Asia countries

Source, made by author based on Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI)

The WGI project uses data from a wide variety of sources, including surveys of households and firms, as well as expert assessments produced by various organisations. The data are normalised to a scale ranging from approximately -2.5 to 2.5, with higher values corresponding to better governance outcomes. The figures presented in Figure 6 illustrate the

institutional factors in Africa and Asia, including Political Stability, Voice and Accountability, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, Government Effectiveness, and Control of Corruption, from 2010 to 2018. These factors are critical in shaping the economic landscape of these regions and significantly influence China's outward foreign direct investment (OFDI) and export trade. Understanding the trends in these institutional factors provides insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by Chinese enterprises in Africa and Asia. This analysis aims to explain the figures in the context of China's OFDI and export trade, highlighting the implications of these institutional factors on economic activities. Political Stability in Figure 6 shows a general decline from 2010 to 2018, with notable fluctuations. Political stability is a critical factor for investment decisions, as it affects the predictability and security of the business environment. For Chinese investors, political instability can pose significant risks, including disruptions to operations, policy changes, and security concerns. The decline in political stability in these regions may have deterred some Chinese investments, particularly in sectors that require substantial capital and long-term commitments.

Voice and Accountability depicts the trend in Voice and Accountability, which shows a slight improvement from 2010 to 2018. Voice and Accountability reflect the extent to which citizens can participate in selecting their government, as well as freedom of expression, association, and media. Higher levels of voice and accountability are associated with better governance and more transparent business environments. For Chinese OFDI, improvements in this area can lead to a more favourable investment climate by reducing risks related to governance and enhancing the protection of investors' rights.

Regulatory Quality indicates an overall decline with some fluctuations. Regulatory quality measures the ability of the government to formulate and implement sound policies and regulations that permit and promote private sector development. A decline in regulatory quality can hinder business operations, increase compliance costs, and create uncertainties for investors. For Chinese exporters and investors, weak regulatory environments can pose challenges in terms of navigating complex and inconsistent regulations. Nonetheless, China's extensive experience in dealing with diverse regulatory frameworks and its strategy of building strong bilateral ties can mitigate some of these challenges.

Rule of Law shows an improvement from 2010 to 2014, followed by a decline. The Rule of Law indicator reflects the extent to which agents have confidence in and abide by the rules of society, including the quality of contract enforcement, property rights, and the courts, as well as the likelihood of crime and violence. A strong rule of law is essential for protecting investments and ensuring fair treatment of businesses. Improvements in this area can attract Chinese OFDI by providing a more secure environment for business operations. However, the subsequent decline may raise concerns about the sustainability of these improvements and the long-term security of investments.

Government Effectiveness indicates fluctuations with an overall slight improvement. Government Effectiveness captures perceptions of the quality of public services, the quality of the civil service and its independence from political pressures, the quality of policy formulation and implementation, and the credibility of the government's commitment to such policies. Effective governance is crucial for creating a conducive environment for business and investment.

Control of Corruption shows an overall decline with significant fluctuations. Control of Corruption reflects the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain, including both petty and grand forms of corruption, as well as the capture of the state by elites and private interests. High levels of corruption can deter investment by increasing costs and risks.

4 Conclusion

The institutional factors illustrated in the figures play a crucial role in shaping the economic landscape of Africa and Asia, impacting China's OFDI and export trade. Political stability, regulatory quality, rule of law, government effectiveness, and control of corruption are critical determinants of the investment climate. While improvements in these areas can attract Chinese investment and facilitate trade, declines or instability can pose significant challenges. By understanding the trends in these institutional factors, policymakers and businesses can better navigate the complexities of investing and trading in Africa and Asia.

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References

[1] <http://english.mofcom.gov.cn/article/newsrelease/press/202311/20231103452116.shtml>

[2] <https://unctad.org/publication/world-investment-report-2023>

[3] <https://www.aei-conference.org/>

[4] <https://www.china-briefing.com/>

[5] Africa China Economy. (2023). <https://africachinapresscentre.org/2023/11/03/china-africa-to-keep-deepening-industrial-chain-cooperation/>

[6] <https://www.sais-cari.org/chinese-investment-in-africa>

[7] Asian Development Bank (ADB). (2023). Asian Economic Integration Report